

Development of an Updated Spot Map and Evacuation Map for Barangay Dontogan Using Operations Research-Based Shortest Route Analysis

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Abstract: In Baguio City, Barangay Dontogan is particularly susceptible to landslides and slope instability because of its mountainous terrain, steep slopes, and increasing urban development. Despite these risks, the barangay continues to rely on an outdated spot map that no longer accurately reflects current infrastructures, residential areas, and evacuation routes. Additionally, no updated evacuation map is available for residents during emergency situations. This study aimed to develop an updated spot map and a functional evacuation map for the ten puroks of Barangay Dontogan to strengthen disaster preparedness and emergency response. Using a descriptive-developmental research design, data were gathered through surveys, interviews, field observations, and official records from barangay and city offices. Purposive sampling was utilized in selecting barangay officials and members of the Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (BDRRMC) as key informants. Operations Research tools, particularly the shortest route method and supply-demand analysis, were applied to identify the most efficient evacuation routes and assess the adequacy of evacuation centers relative to the projected number of evacuees. Findings of the study are expected to identify deficiencies in the current spot map and evacuation system, determine the accommodation capacity of evacuation facilities per purok, and establish the shortest and most accessible evacuation routes for residents. The resulting maps may serve as official references for Barangay Dontogan and the Baguio City Local Government Unit in disaster planning and community risk reduction initiatives.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

The Philippines is considered one of the most disaster-prone countries in the world due to its geographic location, climatic conditions, and geological features. Over the years, the country has experienced an increasing occurrence of natural hazards that have caused significant damage to lives, properties, infrastructure, and the environment (Rathore, 2025). Most recently, as of November 19, 2025, the reported death toll from Typhoon Uwan has risen to 33, with many fatalities still undergoing validation (Nepomuceno, 2025). Rapid population growth, urban expansion, environmental degradation, and climate change have significantly intensified the impacts of these hazards, elevating disaster risk reduction to a critical national priority—particularly in the face of limited government action, where resilience is often promoted more prominently than accountability (Gita-Carlos, 2024).

Since the Philippines is situated along the Pacific Ring of Fire (see Figure 1.1), it consistently ranked among the most disaster-prone countries in the world due to its exposure to both geophysical and hydrometeorological hazards. Its location in the western Pacific makes it vulnerable to frequent typhoons, while its position along active tectonic boundaries exposes it to earthquakes and volcanic activity. The combination of natural exposure, population growth, environmental degradation, and unplanned development increases the overall disaster risk of many communities across the country.

Figure 1.1. Map of the Pacific Ring of Fire including tectonic plate boundaries

To address these challenges, the Philippine government established a comprehensive legal framework for disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) (Department of the Interior and Local Government, 2011-2028). A key policy is Republic Act No. 10121, also known as the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010. This law institutionalized a proactive and community-based approach to disaster preparedness, prevention, mitigation, response, and recovery. It also led to the creation of the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC), which coordinates disaster risk management efforts at the national and local levels. The law emphasizes the importance of hazard assessment, risk mapping, and integration of DRRM into local development planning.

In the local context, Baguio City presents unique geographic and climatic conditions that influence its disaster

risk profile. Situated in the Cordillera mountain range, the city is characterized by steep slopes, elevated terrain, and highly dissected landscapes. Its mountainous topography makes many areas susceptible to slope instability, especially during periods of intense or prolonged rainfall (Ching, 2025). The combination of saturated soils, steep terrain, and human activities such as land conversion and construction increases the likelihood of landslides and soil erosion (Jaafari, 2024). Historically, the city has recorded several incidents of slope failure, infrastructure damage, and displacement of residents due to heavy rains and ground movement (Agoot, 2025a; Agoot, 2025b; Aguilar, 2025). These recurring events highlight the importance of localized hazard assessment and mapping to reduce vulnerability and strengthen community resilience.

Barangay Dontogan is one of the bigger rural barangays located in the southern portion of Baguio City, housing 6609 civilians as of the 2023 census (PhilAtlas). It serves as a transitional area between the highly urbanized sections of the city and the more agricultural municipalities of Benguet. The barangay is accessible through major road networks connecting it to the city proper and neighboring communities. From Igorot Park, it only takes one jeepney ride from the city center to reach the barangay. The barangay is characterized by predominantly mountainous and rolling terrain, with varying elevations and steep slopes. The topography includes ridges, valleys, and sloping lands that influence land use and settlement distribution. Such physical features make certain portions of the barangay susceptible to erosion and slope instability, particularly during periods of intense rainfall.

Figure 1.2. Map boundary of Brgy. Dontogan

Certain populations and infrastructure in Barangay Dontogan are particularly vulnerable as mentioned by the appointed Barangay Secretary. Households situated on steep slopes, near waterways, or in areas with poor drainage are at greater risk during heavy rains. Infrastructure such as roads, bridges, schools, and utility lines may also be affected by slope instability and flooding. Damage to these facilities can disrupt transportation, access to education, delivery of basic services, and emergency response operations. These realities emphasize the urgent need for comprehensive hazard mapping and risk assessment to identify high-risk zones and guide mitigation measures.

Hazard maps are specialized tools that identify and illustrate areas susceptible to natural hazards such as landslides, flooding, earthquakes, and other environmental

threats (Lee, 2025). In countries like the Philippines, hazard mapping is an essential component of disaster risk reduction and management as it provides visual and data-driven information to guide decision-making at national and local levels (Pacific Disaster Center, 2021). One of the primary purposes of hazard maps is the identification of high-risk zones. By categorizing areas into different risk levels—such as low, moderate, or high susceptibility—hazard maps enable communities and local authorities to clearly recognize which locations are most vulnerable. From these hazard maps, an evacuation map will be made.

On the other hand, an evacuation map is a visual guide designed to help people safely exit a building, area, or region during an emergency such as a fire, flood, or other hazards. It clearly shows exit routes, emergency exits, and safe assembly points where people should gather after evacuating (Stogner, 2024). Evacuation maps often highlight areas to avoid, such as fire-prone zones or chemical storage, and may indicate the locations of safety equipment like fire extinguishers or first aid kits. These maps are commonly displayed in public spaces, ensuring that anyone can quickly understand the safest path to safety. However, Brgy. Dontogan has yet to provide its residents with an updated spot map and a detailed evacuation plan. At present, only updated hazard maps are publicly available, while the spot map used by Brgy. Dontogan remains outdated, having not been revised for the past 10 years.

For areas that are highly vulnerable and geographically complex, such as Barangay Dontogan in Baguio City, Philippines, having a well-designed spot map and evacuation plan is particularly indispensable. While hazard maps provide general information, they may not capture site-specific conditions and instability that evacuation maps focus on. Therefore, this study is undertaken to develop detailed and localized evacuation maps tailored specifically to the 10 districts (purok) of Barangay Dontogan to assist barangay officials and the Baguio City Local Government Unit (LGU) in evidence-based disaster planning and decision-making.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Barangay Dontogan in Baguio City is located in an area that is prone to landslides and earthquakes. Because of its steep terrain, disasters can cause serious damage and put residents at risk. However, the barangay is still using a spot map that is already ten years outdated. This old spot map may no longer show the correct roads, houses, buildings, and danger zones, which may cause confusion to future residents and tourists. There is also no evacuation map available to the citizens of Brgy. Dontogan to be used during emergencies.

In line with the aforementioned, the researchers aim to examine the current spot map, evacuation facilities, and routes of Barangay Dontogan in order to create an updated and detailed spot map as well as a functional evacuation map ready for use.

The study aims to address the following research questions:

1. What improvements can be made to the current spot map of Brgy. Dontogan?

2. How do the observed issues in the current spot map of Brgy. Dontogan affect its functionality?
3. What percentage of the current population of the residents can the available evacuation facilities per purok accommodate?
4. What are the shortest evacuation routes available to the residents per purok?

1.3 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study aims to improve the disaster preparedness and evacuation planning of Barangay Dontogan through the development of an updated spot map and a functional evacuation map. By examining the current spot map, evacuation facilities, and evacuation routes within the barangay, the study seeks to identify existing issues and provide practical solutions that can enhance the safety and welfare of residents during emergencies and disasters.

Additionally, it contributes to the existing body of knowledge in the fields of disaster risk reduction and community planning. It provides insights into the importance of updated spot maps and evacuation systems in ensuring effective disaster response. The findings may also serve as a reference for future researchers who wish to conduct similar studies related to evacuation mapping and disaster management in local communities with the use of Operations Research tools.

The study will benefit the following groups and sectors within the community:

1. **Barangay Officials and Local Government Units (LGUs).** The updated spot map and evacuation map can help local officials improve disaster preparedness plans, identify deficiencies in evacuation facilities, and implement more efficient emergency response strategies. The approved maps may also be incorporated into Barangay Dontogan's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Report and be utilized as the barangay's official functional maps for disaster response and evacuation operations.
2. **Residents of Barangay Dontogan.** The study will help residents become more aware of the nearest and safest evacuation routes and facilities available in their respective puroks. This can reduce confusion and panic during disasters and improve community safety.
3. **Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Personnel.** The findings of the study can assist DRRM personnel in assessing the capacity of evacuation facilities and identifying residents who may not be accommodated during emergencies.
4. **Future Researchers.** The study may serve as a guide or basis for future studies concerning evacuation systems, hazard mapping, and disaster preparedness in other barangays with the use of Operations Research.

Furthermore, this research may open opportunities for further studies involving advanced mapping technologies, evacuation simulations, hazard vulnerability assessments, and disaster resilience planning. Future researchers may also expand the study by integrating Geographic Information Systems (GIS), real-time disaster

monitoring, or population forecasting to further improve evacuation planning and community preparedness.

2. Method

2.1 Research Design and Methodology

The research methodology of the study utilizes a descriptive-developmental research design employing quantitative and qualitative. The descriptive method was utilized to systematically identify, collect, and present relevant information regarding the physical features of the community, including roads, residential areas, public establishments, and available evacuation centers as provided by the Barangay Secretary. Descriptive research is appropriate in studies that aim to describe existing conditions and situations as they naturally occur (Sirisilla, 2023).

The developmental aspect of the study focused on the design and preparation of the spot map and evacuation map intended to support disaster preparedness and emergency response of Brgy. Dontogan. The spot map was developed to present important landmarks and facilities within the community (National Nutrition Council Region 7, 2026). However, danger zones were not included in the spot map since official hazard maps provided by concerned government agencies were already available and served as the basis for identifying hazard-prone areas.

Furthermore, operations research tools were applied in the development of the evacuation map. Specifically, the shortest route method was utilized to determine the most efficient and accessible evacuation routes from residential areas to available evacuation centers. This method enabled the researchers to identify routes that minimize travel distance and evacuation time during emergency situations. In addition, supply and demand analysis was employed to evaluate the relationship between the capacity of evacuation centers and the estimated number of evacuees. The supply represented the available capacity of evacuation centers, while the demand referred to the projected number of individuals requiring evacuation during disasters. According to Jerabek et. al (2020), Operations Research (OR) applies mathematical models and optimization algorithms to identify efficient routes and reduce transportation costs. By representing destinations as nodes and road connections as arcs, OR methods improve the efficiency of transportation systems which will be beneficial in mapping an evacuation plan.

2.2 SAMPLING METHOD AND SAMPLING SIZE

This study will employ the entire population and geographic area of Barangay Dontogan in Baguio City will be included in the research. Since all households, hazard-prone areas, evacuation routes, and designated evacuation sites within the barangay will be covered, no sampling in the traditional sense will be conducted. The use of complete enumeration will ensure that the spot map to be developed reflects the actual and comprehensive condition of the community. By involving the whole barangay, the study will be able to capture the full extent of the accessibility of evacuation facilities for the evacuation plan and newly-built landmarks and households for the spot map.

This approach will increase the reliability and practical relevance of the resulting spot map and evacuation plan.

Specifically, all residential households, both old and new, will be identified and plotted. All existing road networks that may serve as evacuation routes will also be mapped and assessed in terms of accessibility and connectivity to safe areas. Furthermore, all officially designated evacuation sites within the barangay will be included and evaluated based on location, capacity, and accessibility. Through this comprehensive coverage, the study will ensure that no area or population group will be excluded from the disaster risk assessment.

The study will involve key informants composed of selected barangay officials and members of the Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (BDRRMC) of Barangay Dontogan in Baguio City. These key informants will include the Barangay Captain, designated council members overseeing disaster risk reduction and management, and active BDRRMC personnel who are directly responsible for planning, coordination, and implementation of disaster-related programs within the community. Their participation will be essential because they possess firsthand knowledge of the barangay's history, existing measures, available resources, and operational evacuation procedures.

These individuals will be intentionally selected through purposive sampling due to their direct involvement in disaster preparedness, emergency response planning, and community safety initiatives. As policy-makers and implementers at the barangay level, they will provide verified information regarding officially designated evacuation routes and centers, past disaster experiences, early warning systems, and logistical arrangements during emergencies. Their insights will also help validate the accuracy of the spot map as well as the evacuation map and ensure that the framework to be developed aligns with existing barangay protocols and local government guidelines.

2.3 DATA-GATHERING METHOD

The making of evacuation and spot map needs the present resources and information of Barangay Dontogan such as maps, aerial view, parameters and population in each zone and of the whole barangay, the procedures in times of disasters and calamities, and problems faced by the barangay officials as they follow and conduct risk reduction management. This data provides a thorough understanding of the current situation of the barangay. It also allows in depth analysis with the purpose of addressing these problems through optimal solutions.

The structured pre and post assessment questionnaires in Appendix B will be used to collect and evaluate the current evacuation map and facilities, spot map and evacuation routes and the implementation of new spot and evacuation map. The questionnaire uses a likert scale ranging from five to one, *excellent to needs improvement* respectively. The questionnaires have same questions and response options for all respondents so this ensures uniformity, eases comparison and comprehension through statistical analysis. The data gathered will be used to assess the capability and effectivity of the current evacuation map, facilities, and spot map. Through this, the newly developed spot and evacuation map will address its inadequacies and help the Barangay in building a safer community even in times of disasters and calamities.

Surveys and numbers alone cannot capture all the data needed in this research, especially the past experiences which require in depth answers from an individual to further understand the situation. Hence, interviews will also be conducted with the representatives of the barangay who thoroughly experience and understand the needs of the Barangay and be able to communicate it articulately. The researchers connect with the secretary of Barangay Dontogan who supports and assists as they gather the needed information. Through the interview, the current evacuation facilities, routes, procedures and spot map are explained profoundly which also open more discussions to further comprehend the concepts. This improves data quality and authenticity.

Through interviews, more data needed for the spot and evacuation map are coordinated with the researchers. The barangay secretary connects us with different city offices, namely, City Buildings and Architecture Office (CBAO), City Assessor's Office (CAO) and City Planning and Development Office (CPDO) for the needed information such as the aerial view of the barangay for the visualization and analyzation of the routes, and parameters and population of each zones to accommodate the residents and provide near evacuation facilities. Moreover, all data that will be collected will be used solely for the purpose of evaluation and analysis for the making of comprehensive evacuation and spot maps.

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